



Scatter plot showing correlation coefficients of TMM-normalized expression between inparalog pairs versus dS (cophenetic synonymous distances). dS estimations below 2 were considered in this analysis.

To analyze if expression correlation declined with increasing time since duplication (Casneuf et al., 2006; Rogozin, 2014), we studied the association between the estimated correlation values and the synonymous cophenetic distance among inparalogs in *S. mansoni*. We did not find evidence to support this association.